

Supporting Information

Tuning Fluorescence and Singlet Oxygen Generation in Heavy-Atom-Free BODIPYs through Charge-Transfer State Modulation

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Index:

1.	Synthesis of compounds.....	2
	1.1. General procedures.....	2
	1.2. Trimethoxyphenyl derivatives.....	2
	1.3. Trimethylphenyl derivatives.....	5
	1.4. ¹ H and ¹³ C NMR spectra.....	7
2.	Photophysical characterization.....	12
3.	Cyclic voltammetry.....	18
4.	Theoretical calculations.....	18
5.	X-Ray crystallography.....	20
6.	References.....	29

1. Synthesis of compounds

1.1. General Procedures

Chemicals and Solvents

Where appropriate, reactions were carried out under an inert atmosphere of argon with dry solvents, using anhydrous conditions unless otherwise stated. Stainless steel syringes or cannulae were used to transfer air- and moisture-sensitive liquids. Chemicals and solvents were purchased from one of the following providers: SigmaAldrich, Alfa Aesar, Fluka, Fluorochem, Honeywell, Merck, Panreac, Scharlab or TCI. Anhydrous solvents were prepared according to standard methods by distillation over drying agents or via elution through a PureSolv™ column drying system from Innovative Technology, Inc. All other solvents were of HPLC grade and used as provided. Reagents were purchased at the highest commercial quality and used without further purification, unless otherwise stated.

Purification

Flash column chromatography was performed using silica gel (60-Å pore size, 40–63 µm, Merck). Reactions were followed using thin-layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel-coated plates (Merck 60 F254). Detection was performed with UV light and/or by charring at ca. 150 °C after dipping into an aqueous solution of potassium permanganate (KMnO₄), or an ethanolic solution of phosphomolybdic acid (PMA). Yields refer to chromatographically and spectroscopically (¹H-NMR) homogeneous material, unless otherwise stated.

Structural Characterization

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III-400 (400 and 100 MHz, respectively) spectrometer. Chemical shifts are quoted in parts per million from residual solvent peak and coupling constants (*J*) given in Hertz. Multiplicities are abbreviated as: b (broad), s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), m (multiplet) or combinations thereof. Proton and carbon assignments are based on gCOSY, gHSQC and gHMBC correlation experiments. High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were recorded on an Agilent 6520 Accurate Mass Q-TOF instrument with an ESI source. Results are expressed as mass/charge (*m/z*).

1.2. Trimethoxyphenyl derivatives (1a/b-3a/b)

Compound 2a: TMSCN (100 µL, 0.79 mmol, 7.2 eq.) and SnCl₄ (7 µL, 0.06 mmol, 0.5 eq.) were added to a solution of compound **1a**¹ (39.5 mg, 0.11 mmol, 1.0 eq.) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.5

mL) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 40 minutes, then it was washed with H₂O (10 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane/EtOAc 4:1 to hexane/EtOAc 1:4) giving compound **2a** as a red solid (34 mg, 84%).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.84 (2H, s, H3 and H5), 6.86 (2H, dd, *J* = 4.4, 1.2 Hz, H1 and H7), 6.55 (2H, dd, *J* = 4.3, 2.0 Hz, H2 and H6), 6.21 (2H, s, H11 and H13), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH₃12), 3.69 (6H, s, OCH₃10 and OCH₃14).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ = 163.4 (C12), 159.3 (C10 and C14), 145.1 (C3 and C5), 144.2 (C8), 135.2 (C7a and C8a), 131.6 (C1 and C7), 127.6 (dd, *J* = 151.1, 75.7 Hz, 2x BCN), 119.3 (C2 and C6), 102.7 (C9), 90.8 (C11 and C13), 56.0 (OCH₃10 and OCH₃14), 55.7 (OCH₃12).

HRMS (ESI⁺): For C₂₀H₂₁BN₅O₃ (M+NH₄)⁺, *m/z* (calc.) = 390.1736; *m/z* (found) = 390.1714.

Compound 2b: TMSCN (153 μL, 1.22 mmol, 7.2 eq.) and SnCl₄ (10 μL, 0.08 mmol, 0.5 eq.) were added to a solution of compound **1b**² (70 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1.0 eq.) in CH₂Cl₂ (2 mL) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 40 minutes, then it was washed with H₂O (10 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane/EtOAc 4:1 to hexane/EtOAc 1:4) giving compound **2b** as a red solid (68 mg, 94%).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 6.21 (2H, s, H11 and H13), 6.11 (2H, s, H2 and H6), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃12), 3.72 (6H, s, OCH₃10 and OCH₃14), 2.71 (6H, s, CH₃3 and CH₃5), 1.59 (6H, s, CH₃1 and CH₃7).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ (ppm) = 163.4 (C12), 158.3 (C10 and C14), 155.1 (C3 and C5), 143.8 (C1 and C7), 137.8 (C8), 131.0 (C7a and C8a), 127.3 (2 × CN, q, J=73.6 Hz), 122.3 (C2 and C6), 104.4 (C9), 91.4 (C11 and C13), 56.4 (OCH₃10 and OCH₃14), 55.9 (OCH₃12), 15.9 (CH₃3 and CH₃5), 14.3 (CH₃1 and CH₃7).

HRMS (ESI⁺): For C₂₄H₂₅BN₄O₃Na (M+Na)⁺, m/z (calc.) = 451.1916; m/z (found) = 451.1917.

Compound 3a: Compound **1a**¹ (20.2 mg, 0.06 mmol, 1.0 eq.) and oxalic acid (11.6 mg, 0.13 mmol, 2.3 eq.) were suspended in 2.0 mL of CH₃CN, TMSCl (145 μL, 1.1 mmol, 20.0 eq.) was added and the mixture was stirred in a microwave reactor (10 min at 80 °C to 10 min at 100 °C to 30 min at 120 °C). The crude mixture was concentrated and purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane/EtOAc 5:1 to 100% EtOAc), yielding compound **3a** as an orange solid (15.8 mg, 69%).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.57 (2H, t, J=1.7 Hz, H3 and H5), 6.90 (2H, dd, J=4.2, 1.2 Hz, H1 and H7), 6.50 (2H, dd, J=4.2, 2.1 Hz, H2 and H6), 6.22 (2H, s, H11 and H13), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH₃12), 3.69 (6H, s, OCH₃10 and OCH₃14).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ (ppm) = 163.5 (C12), 159.4 (C10 and C14), 158.6 (C1' and C2'), 144.0 (C8), 143.3 (C3 and C5), 137.1 (C7a and C8a), 132.9 (C1 and C7), 119.1 (C2 and C6), 102.8 (C9), 90.8 (C11 and C13), 56.0 (OCH₃10 and OCH₃14), 55.7 (OCH₃12).

HRMS (ESI⁺): For C₂₀H₂₁BN₃O₇ (M+NH₄)⁺, m/z (calc.) = 426.1471; m/z (found) = 426.1466.
For C₂₀H₁₈BN₄O₃ (M+H)⁺, m/z (calc.) = 409.1205; m/z (found) = 409.1200

Compound 3b: Oxalic acid (13 mg, 0.14 mmol, 1.2 eq.) and TMSCl (300 μ L, 2.4 mmol, 20.0 eq.) were added to a suspension of BODIPY **1b**² (50 mg, 0.12 mmol, 1.0 eq.) in CH₃CN (3.0 mL) and the mixture was stirred in a microwave reactor (10 min at 80 °C to 30 min at 120 °C). The crude mixture was concentrated and purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane/EtOAc 5:1 to 100% EtOAc), yielding compound **3b** as an orange solid (50 mg, 89%).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 6.22 (2H, s, H11 and H13), 5.99 (2H, s, H2 and H6), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃12), 3.72 (6H, s, OCH₃10 and OCH₃14), 2.27 (6H, s, CH₃3 and CH₃5), 1.58 (6H, s, CH₃1 and CH₃7).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ = 163.1 (C12), 160.1 (C1' and C2'), 157.9 (C10 and C14), 154.7 (C3 and C5), 144.7 (C1 and C7), 137.8 (C8), 133.4 (C7a and C8a), 122.8 (C2 and C6), 103.9 (C9), 91.1 (C11 and C13), 56.1 (OCH₃10 and OCH₃14), 55.6 (OCH₃12), 15.6 (CH₃3 and CH₃5), 13.9 (CH₃1 and CH₃7).

HRMS (ESI⁺): For C₂₄H₂₉BN₃O₇ (M+NH₄)⁺, m/z (calc.) = 482.2097; m/z (found) = 482.2095.

1.3. Trimethylphenyl derivatives (4a/b-5a/b)

Compound 5a: TMSCN (288 μ L, 2.32 mmol, 7.2 eq.) and SnCl₄ (17 μ L, 0.16 mmol, 0.5 eq.) were added to a solution of compound **4a**³ (100 mg, 0.32 mmol, 1.0 eq.) in CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 50 minutes, then it was washed with H₂O (10 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane/EtOAc 4:1 to hexane/EtOAc 1:1) giving compound **5a** as a red solid (86 mg, 83%).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.94 (2H, s, H3 and H5), 6.90 (2H, s, H11 and H13), 6.80 (2H, dd, J = 4.4, 1.2 Hz, H1 and H7), 6.62 (2H, dd, J = 4.3, 2.0 Hz, H2 and H6), 2,37 (3H, s, CH₃12), 2.09 (6H, s, CH₃10 and CH₃14).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ = 149.6 (C9), 146.2 (C3 and C5), 139.7 (12), 136.2 (C8), 134.1 (C7a and C8a), 131.5 (C1 and C7), 128.7 (C10 and C14), 128.5 (C11 and C13), 126.8 (dd, J =151.1, 75.7 Hz, 2x BCN), 120.2 (C2 and C6), 21,3 (CH₃C12), 20.1 (CH₃C10 and CH₃C14).

HRMS (ESI⁺): For C₄₀H₃₄B₂N₈Na (2M+Na)⁺, m/z (calc.) = 671.2998; m/z (found) = 671.2990.

Compound 5b

The synthesis procedure and characterization data for compound **5b** are described in ref.⁴.

1.4. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of compounds 1a,b-4a,b.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound 2a

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound 2a

¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **2b**

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **2b**.

¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **3a**.

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **3a**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **3b**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **3b**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of compound **5a**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of compound **5a**.

2. Photophysical characterization

Absorption spectra were recorded by UV-Vis-NIR Spectroscopy (model Cary 7000, Agilent Technologies, Madrid, Spain) equipped with two lamps (a halogen lamp for the Vis-IR region and a deuterium lamp for the UV region).

Fluorescence measurements were recorded with an Edinburgh Instruments spectrofluorimeter (FLSP920 model, Livingston, UK) equipped with a xenon flash lamp (450 W) as the excitation source. Fluorescence spectra were corrected from the wavelength dependence on the detector sensibility. The fluorescence quantum yields of the photosensitizers were measured by a relative method, using pyromethene 567 ($\Phi = 0.84$ in EtOH) as a standard sample). Radiative decay curves were recorded in the same Edinburgh Instruments spectrofluorimeter (FLSP920, Livingston, UK) by Time-Correlated Single-Photon Counting Technique (TC-SPC), using a microchannel plate detector (Hamamatsu C4878) with picoseconds time resolution (~ 100 ps). Fluorescence decay curves were monitored at the maximum emission wavelength after excitation using a Fianium super continuous wavelength tunable-laser with 150 ps FWHM pulses.

Singlet oxygen quantum yield (Φ_{Δ}) was determined by direct method measuring its phosphorescence at 1276 nm employing a NIR detector (InGaAs detector, Hamamatsu G8605-23), integrated into the same Edinburgh spectrofluorimeter upon continuous monochromatic excitation (450 W Xenon lamp) of the sample in 1 cm cells in front configuration (front face), 40° and 50° to the excitation and emission beams, respectively, and leaned 30° to the plane formed by the direction of incidence. The value was obtained by the media of at least five different concentrations (range from 2×10^{-6} M to 5×10^{-5} M) and using commercial photosensitizer 8-methylthio-2,6-diiodobodipy⁵ (MeSBDP, CAS-1835282-63-7, $\Phi_{\Delta} = 0.95$ in ACN) as reference.

Femtosecond TA (fs-TA) measurements were performed in solutions of 1a, 2a (MeOH), at concentrations in the order of $XX \times 10^{-4}$ M. Samples were prepared in a 1 mm fused silica cuvette and continuously scanned through the focal plane to avoid thermal effects on the sample. The ultrashort laser pulses (1 KHz train of 35 fs pulses at 800nm) were generated in an oscillator-regenerative amplifier laser system (Coherent, Mantis-Legend). The pump pulses at 505 nm were obtained by means of sum frequency of the fundamental 800 nm and the signal beam of an optical parametric amplifier (OPA), while the white light continuum probe (320 nm-1100 nm) is produced by focusing a small fraction of the amplifier output onto a 2 mm thick CaF₂ window. The relative delay between the pump and probe pulses is achieved with a translation stage (Thorlabs, DDS220) that allows a maximum delay of 2 ns. Transient absorbance is measured with

a fiber-coupled dual channel spectrometer (Avantes, Avaspec) as a function of the pump-probe delay.

Nanosecond Transient absorption spectra (ns-TA) and triplet state lifetimes (τ^T) were recorded in Laser Flash Photolysis (LP980, Edinburgh Instruments). Samples were excited with a computer-controlled Nd:YAG laser coupled to OPO system from LOTIS (TII 2134) operating at 1 Hz and with a pulse width of 7 ns. The transient spectra were registered in spectral mode with ICCD (Andor's iStar DH320T) and the kinetic decay curves in a PMT detector (Hamamatsu R928). Triplet lifetimes were obtained from the corresponding decay of the triplet transient band at the absorption maximum in the presence (aerated solutions) and absence of oxygen (de-aerated solution). Data were analyzed using the LP900 software.

Table S1 Photophysical properties of BODIPYs **1a/b-5a/b**. λ_{ab} : Absorption peak wavelength; ϵ : Molar absorption coefficient at peak; λ_{fl} : Fluorescence peak wavelength upon excitation at 490 nm; Φ : Fluorescence quantum yield; τ : Fluorescence lifetime; Φ_{Δ} : Singlet oxygen quantum yield

Compound	Solvent	λ_{ab} (nm)	ϵ_{max} ($10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	λ_{fl} (nm)	Φ	τ (ns)	Φ_{Δ}
1a	Toluene	507.0	6.1	522.5	0.85	5.41	0.12
	Chloroform	507.0	6.6	523.5	0.68	5.13	0.25
	Acetone	502.0	6.4	518.0	0.01	0.003 (96%) 1.01 (4%)	0.35
	Methanol	501.5	5.8	517.0	0.004	0.389 (98%) 0.008 (2%)	0.20
	PBS	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
2a	Toluene	512.0	6.6	529.0	0.38	3.32	0.28
	Chloroform	510.5	6.1	526.5	0.07	1.76 (94%) 5.52 (6%)	0.75
	Acetone	506.5	6.3	517.0	0.01	0.52 (22%) 4.85 (78%)	0.12
	Methanol	505.5	5.7	515.0	0.002	0.03 (78%) 1.17 (14%) 5.43 (8%)	0.07
	PBS	506.0	1.8	516.0 592.0	0.012	N.A.	N.A.
3a	Toluene	515.5	5.6	530.5	0.51	4.14 (96%) 0.83 (4%)	0.38
	Chloroform	514.0	5.3	528.5	0.03	1.51 (55%) 0.07 (41%) 4.89 (4%)	0.65
	Acetone	509.5	5.3	516.0	0.006	0.24 (51%)	N.A.*

Compound	Solvent	λ_{ab} (nm)	ϵ_{max} ($10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	λ_{fl} (nm)	Φ	τ (ns)	Φ_{Δ}
						2.82 (25%) 5.55 (24%)	
	Methanol	508.5	4.9	517.0	0.013	1.13 (97%) 5.13 (3%)	0.11*
	PBS	500.5	2.4	512.5 578.0	0.002	0.003	N.A.
1b	Toluene	509.5	10.8	521.0	0.90	5.10	N.A.
	Chloroform	508.5	9.7	519.5	0.89	5.85	0.03
	Acetone	503.5	10.4	514.5	0.84	6.27	N.A.
	Methanol	503.5	9.4	513.5	0.85	6.52	N.A.
	PBS	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
2b	Toluene	509.5	11.2	520.5	0.91	5.34	N.A.
	Chloroform	508.0	10.7	517.5	0.92	6.13	N.A.
	Acetone	503.5	10.9	512.5	0.40	4.60	0.27
	Methanol	503.0	10.2	512.0	0.34	3.89	0.30
	PBS	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
3b	Toluene	515.0	8.8	526.5	0.90	5.71	N.A.
	Chloroform	513.0	8.8	522.5	0.82	6.48	0
	Acetone	508.5	8.4	518.5	0.27	3.00 (71%) 5.33 (29%)	0.48
	Methanol	508.5	8.4	518.0	0.19	1.98 (76%) 5.86 (24%)	0.26
	PBS	500.5 (564)	1.4	511.5	0.13	5.11 (94%) 0.97 (6%)	N.A.
4a	Toluene	503.5	6.56	515.5	0.85	7.24	N.A.
	Chloroform	502.0	6.57	514.0	0.83	7.27	N.A.
	Acetone	498.5	6.07	511.0	0.84	7.35	N.A.
	Methanol	498.0	5.94	510.5	0.84	7.57	N.A.
4b	Toluene	504.5	8.60	514.0	0.93	6.25	N.A.
	Chloroform	503.5	8.77	512.5	0.93	5.60	N.A.
	Acetone	499.5	8.64	508.5	0.92	5.95	N.A.
	Methanol	499.0	8.34	508.0	0,80	6.20	N.A.
5a	Toluene	507.0	5.82	521.5	0.85	6.69	N.A.
	Chloroform	505.0	6.14	517.0	0.84	7.46	N.A.
	Acetone	502.0	5.52	514.5	0,82	7.65	N.A.

Compound	Solvent	λ_{ab} (nm)	ϵ_{max} ($10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	λ_{fl} (nm)	Φ	τ (ns)	Φ_{Δ}
5b	Methanol	501,5	5.46	512.5	0.80	7.92	N.A.
	Toluene	504.0	8.78	513.5	0.97	5.95	N.A.
	Chloroform	502.5	9.31	511.0	0.95	5.79	N.A.
	Acetone	499.0	8.74	508.5	0.93	6.31	N.A.
	Methanol	498.5	8.69	507.0	0.93	6.59	N.A.

*These compounds underwent photodegradation during singlet oxygen measurements, so no reliable Φ_{Δ} values could be obtained

Figure S1. Absorption and fluorescence spectra in different solvents (black: toluene, red: chloroform, green: acetone and blue: methanol) of compounds **4a-b** and **5a-b**.

Figure S2. Transient spectra of **2b**, **2a** and **1a** in chloroform, and methanol at selected pump probe delays. The shaded area covers the spectral region affected by the pump laser induced scattering.

Figure S3. Top) Transient absorption spectra of **1a** (grey) and **2a** (black) in chloroform (left) and methanol (right); **Bottom)** Decay curve of **1a** transient triplet band at 420 nm in deaerated (left) and after bubbling with air (gray) and with pure oxygen (red) in chloroform

Table S2. Triplet lifetimes in nitrogen-, air- and oxygen-saturated samples and bimolecular rate constants of triplet quenching by molecular oxygen for BODIPYs **1a**, **2a-b** and **3a**.

Compound	Solvent	τ_0^T (μs)	τ_{air}^T (ns)	$\tau_{O_2}^T$ (ns)	k_{q,O_2}^T ($10^{-9} \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)
1a	Toluene	207.5	553	119	0.93
	Chloroform	178.8	410	93	0.92
	Methanol	66.0	285	60	1.63
2a	Toluene	128.5	356	116	0.92
	Chloroform	115.3	467	97	0.89
	Methanol	63.0	288	61	1.60
3a	Toluene	217.0	387	87	1.27
	Chloroform	188.0	467	97	0.88
	Methanol	56.8	351	67	1.50
2b	Methanol	52.5	311	79	1.24
3b	Methanol	56.3	306	76	1.29

3. Cyclic Voltammetry

Electrochemical properties were measured by cyclic voltammetry (Metrohm Autolab) using a three-electrode setup with a platinum disk (diameter 3 mm) working electrode, platinum wire as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. Scan rate was set at 0.2V/s. A 0.1 M solution of tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF6) in dry acetonitrile was used as the electrolyte solvent in which the compounds were dissolved to achieve a concentration of 5 mM. All redox potentials were reported vs ferrocene as internal standard. The solutions were purged with argon and all the measurements were performed under an inert atmosphere.

4. Theoretical calculations

All geometries were optimized at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level of theory⁶ within the framework of density functional theory (DFT) for the ground state, and using time-dependent DFT (TDDFT) for the excited states, S_1 and S_2 . Solvation effects (chloroform and methanol) were simulated by means of the polarizable continuum model (PCM) with the integral equation formalism (IEFPCM).⁷ All structures have been characterized as real local minima of the potential energy surface on the basis of their positive vibrational force constants. Vertical excitations energies to the low-lying excited singlet and triplet states were evaluated at the same level of theory and spin-orbit coupling constants (SOCs) between relevant states was computed using the one-electron Breit Pauli Hamiltonian algorithm⁸. All calculations were performed using the Gaussian 16 software package⁹ and Q-Chem 6.0.1 code¹⁰. The DrawMol program was used for visualization of the molecular orbitals (www.unamur.be/drawmol)

Table S3. Dihedral angle (in degrees) between the BODIPY core and the *meso*-substituent of compounds **1a**, **2a**, **2b** in their ground and LE/CT (local excitation/charge transfer) excited state geometries, calculated at the at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level of theory in chloroform and methanol.

	1a	2a	2b
	Chloroform		
S_0	72	69	90
LE	62	-	77
CT	91	90	-
	Methanol		
S_0	71	68	85
LE	63	-	79
CT	90	90	-

Figure S4. Frontier molecular orbitals of **2a** involved in the main contributions to S_1 (LE, HOMO→LUMO) and S_2 (CT, HOMO-1→LUMO) excited states computed at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level in chloroform.

Figure S5. Frontier molecular orbitals of **2b** involved in the main contributions to S_1 (LE, HOMO→LUMO) and S_2 (CT, HOMO-1→LUMO) excited states computed at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level in chloroform.

Table S4. Molecular orbitals energy (eV) of **1a**, **2a** and **2b** at their respective ground state geometries computed at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level in chloroform and methanol.

	chl			meoh		
	1a	2a	2b	1a	2a	2b
LUMO	-1.82	-2.08	-1.66	-1.92	-2.12	-1.73
HOMO	-7.14	-7.41	-6.90	-7.25	-7.45	-6.97
HOMO-1	-7.47	-7.56	-7.48	-7.47	-7.52	-7.45
gap H/L	5.32	5.33	5.24	5.33	5.33	5.25
gap H-1/L	5.65	5.48	5.82	5.55	5.40	5.72

Table S5. Vertical de-excitation energies (eV) and associated oscillator strengths (in parenthesis) of **1a**, **2a** and **2b** at their relaxed excited state geometries (¹CT and/or ¹LE) computed at the CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level of theory in chloroform and methanol.

Molecule	Geometry	in chloroform		in methanol	
		CT	LE	CT	LE
1a	¹ CT	2.38 (0.00)	2.86 (0.66)	2.27 (0.00)	2.75 (0.75)
	¹ LE	3.03 (0.18)	2.72 (0.58)	2.93 (0.20)	2.62 (0.66)
2a	¹ CT	2.23 (0.00)	2.86 (0.61)	2.15 (0.00)	2.75 (0.70)
2b	¹ LE	3.21 (0.06)	2.68 (0.67)	3.12 (0.05)	2.58 (0.77)

Table S6. Singlet-triplet energy differences ($\Delta E_{ST} = E(T_n) - E(^1CT)$), in eV and SOCs (in cm⁻¹) and state character of **1a** and **2a** computed at the ¹CT optimized geometry and of **2b** at the ¹LE optimized geometry with CAM-B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level in chloroform and methanol. Triplet state character indicated as trimethoxyphenyl-to-BODIPY excitation (CT) or BODIPY local (LE).

T _n	1a			2a			2b		
	char.	ΔE_{ST}	SOC	char.	ΔE_{ST}	SOC	char.	ΔE_{ST}	SOC
in chloroform									
T ₁	LE	-1.01	2.58	LE	-0.84	2.48	LE	-1.55	0.03
T ₂	CT	-0.03	0.07	CT	-0.03	0.10	LE/CT	0.14	0.74
T ₃	LE	0.35	2.30	LE	0.45	0.78	CT/LE	0.35	1.60
T ₄	LE	0.46	0.97	LE	0.63	2.39	LE/CT	0.38	0.35
in methanol									
T ₁	LE	-0.89	2.58	LE/CT	-0.74	2.48	LE	-1.58	0.04
T ₂	CT	-0.03	0.09	CT	-0.03	0.01	LE/CT	0.09	0.79
T ₃	LE	0.47	2.32	LE	0.54	0.83	CT/LE	0.27	1.61
T ₄	LE	0.59	0.96	LE	0.71	2.41	CT	0.31	0.17

5. X-Ray crystallography

Suitable single crystals, obtained through crystallization in CH₂Cl₂/hexane mixtures, were selected and mounted on a SuperNova, Dual, Cu at home/near, HyPix diffractometer. The crystals were kept at 170 (10) K during data collection. Using the Olex2 software,¹¹ the structures were solved with the SHELXT structure solution program,¹² applying Intrinsic Phasing, and refined with the SHELXL refinement package with Least Squares minimization.

Crystal Data for **1a**, C₁₈H₁₇BN₂O₃F₂ (*M* = 358.14 g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), *a* = 9.5105(4) Å, *b* = 9.5664(4) Å, *c* = 10.3957(4) Å, α = 63.622(4)°, β = 84.463(4)°, γ = 79.920(4)°, *V* = 834.07(6) Å³, *Z* = 2, *T* = 170.00(10) K, μ (CuK α) = 0.940 mm⁻¹, *D*_{calc} = 1.426 g/cm³, 7553 reflections measured (9.448° ≤ 2 θ ≤ 137.994°), 3107 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0210, *R*_{sigma} = 0.0244) which were used in all calculations. The final *R*₁ was 0.0447 (*I* > 2 σ (*I*)) and *wR*₂ was 0.1199 (all data).

Crystal Data for **2a**, $C_{20}H_{17}BN_4O_3$ ($M = 372.18$ g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), $a = 10.6991(5)$ Å, $b = 13.1498(6)$ Å, $c = 15.2841(8)$ Å, $\alpha = 79.383(4)^\circ$, $\beta = 73.729(5)^\circ$, $\gamma = 70.223(4)^\circ$, $V = 1932.90(16)$ Å³, $Z = 4$, $T = 170.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 0.713$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.279$ g/cm³, 18908 reflections measured ($6.054^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 137.958^\circ$), 7157 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0553$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0754$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0560 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1592 (all data).

Crystal Data for **3a**, $C_{41}H_{36}B_2Cl_2N_4O_{14}$ ($M = 901.26$ g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), $a = 11.7548(4)$ Å, $b = 14.3223(6)$ Å, $c = 14.6666(6)$ Å, $\alpha = 97.987(3)^\circ$, $\beta = 110.457(4)^\circ$, $\gamma = 111.618(4)^\circ$, $V = 2046.66(14)$ Å³, $Z = 2$, $T = 170.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Mo K}\alpha) = 0.234$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.462$ g/cm³, 10265 reflections measured ($3.938^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 54^\circ$), 10265 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = ?$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0674$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0646 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1864 (all data).

Crystal Data for **1b**, $C_{22}H_{25}BF_2N_2O_3$ ($M = 414.25$ g/mol): monoclinic, space group C2/c (no. 15), $a = 21.2016(3)$ Å, $b = 7.13862(9)$ Å, $c = 27.9608(4)$ Å, $\beta = 108.2938(17)^\circ$, $V = 4018.00(10)$ Å³, $Z = 8$, $T = 170.01(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 0.854$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.370$ g/cm³, 20057 reflections measured ($6.66^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 147.124^\circ$), 4015 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0333$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0257$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0354 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.0959 (all data).

Crystal Data for **2b** ($M = 428.29$ g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), $a = 9.0878(3)$ Å, $b = 10.9478(4)$ Å, $c = 11.6685(4)$ Å, $\alpha = 106.973(3)^\circ$, $\beta = 91.387(3)^\circ$, $\gamma = 92.478(3)^\circ$, $V = 1108.48(7)$ Å³, $Z = 2$, $T = 170.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Mo K}\alpha) = 0.086$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.283$ g/cm³, 13442 reflections measured ($4.49^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 53.998^\circ$), 4802 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0418$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0424$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0568 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1804 (all data).

Crystal Data for **3b**, $C_{24}H_{25}BN_2O_7$ ($M = 464.27$ g/mol): orthorhombic, space group Pbcn (no. 60), $a = 22.7228(7)$ Å, $b = 7.0845(3)$ Å, $c = 27.2192(16)$ Å, $V = 4381.7(4)$ Å³, $Z = 8$, $T = 170.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 0.854$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.408$ g/cm³, 38678 reflections measured ($6.494^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 137.926^\circ$), 4080 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.1833$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0903$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.1052 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.2900 (all data).

Figure S6. Single crystal X-ray crystallography of compounds A) **1a**, B) **1b**, C) **2a**, D) **2b**, E) **3a**, and F) **3b**. Thermal ellipsoids are shown at the 50% probability level; hydrogen atoms are represented as spheres of fixed radius.

Table S7. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1a**.

Identification code	b20230157_NMB113DUCu
Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BN ₂ O ₃ F ₂
Formula weight	358.14
Temperature/K	170.00 (10)
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	9.5105(4)
b/Å	9.5664(4)
c/Å	10.3957(4)
α/°	63.622(4)
β/°	84.463(4)
γ/°	79.920(4)
Volume/Å ³	834.07(6)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /g/cm ³	1.426
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.940
F(000)	372.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.33 × 0.27 × 0.17
Radiation	CuKα(λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	9.448 to 137.994
Index ranges	-11 ≤ h ≤ 11, -11 ≤ k ≤ 11, -12 ≤ l ≤ 11
Reflections collected	7553
Independent reflections	3107 [R _{int} = 0.0210, R _{sigma} = 0.0244]
Data/restraints/parameters	3107/0/238
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.055
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ(I)]	R ₁ = 0.0447, wR ₂ = 0.1177
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0467, wR ₂ = 0.1199
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.21/-0.35

[a] Weighting scheme: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0751P)^2 + 0.1923P]$ where $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Secondary extinction expression (SHELXL-type): $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table S8. Crystal data and structure refinement for **2a**.

Identification code	b20240161_IM855DUCu
Empirical formula	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ BN ₄ O ₃
Formula weight	372.18
Temperature/K	170.00 (10)
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	10.6991(5)
b/Å	13.1498(6)
c/Å	15.2841(8)
α/°	79.383(4)
β/°	73.729(5)
γ/°	70.223(4)
Volume/Å ³	1932.90(16)
Z	4
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.279
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.713
F(000)	776.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.234 × 0.195 × 0.036
Radiation	Cu Kα(λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.054 to 137.958
Index ranges	-11 ≤ h ≤ 12, -15 ≤ k ≤ 15, -18 ≤ l ≤ 18
Reflections collected	18908
Independent reflections	3157 [R _{int} = 0.0553, R _{sigma} = 0.0754]
Data/restraints/parameters	7157/0/511
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.030
Final R indexes [I >= 2σ(I)]	R ₁ = 0.0560, wR ₂ = 0.1453
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0751, wR ₂ = 0.1592
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.20/-0.24

[a] Weighting scheme:: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0751P)^2 + 0.1923P]$ where $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Secondary extinction expression (SHELXL-type): $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table S9. Crystal data and structure refinement for **3a**.

Identification code	b20230134_NMB17DUMo2B
Empirical formula	C ₄₁ H ₃₆ B ₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₁₄
Formula weight	901.26
Temperature/K	170.00(10)
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	11.7548(4)
b/Å	14.3223(6)
c/Å	14.6666(6)
α/°	97.987(3)
β/°	110.457(4)
γ/°	111.618(4)
Volume/Å ³	2046.66(14)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.462
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.234
F(000)	932.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.407 × 0.182 × 0.1
Radiation	Mo Kα (λ = 0.71073)
2θ range for data collection/°	3.938 to 54
Index ranges	-15 ≤ h ≤ 15, -18 ≤ k ≤ 18, -18 ≤ l ≤ 18
Reflections collected	10265
Independent reflections	10265 [R _{int} = ?, R _{sigma} = 0.0674]
Data/restraints/parameters	10265/24/575
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.981
Final R indexes [I >= 2σ(I)]	R ₁ = 0.0646, wR ₂ = 0.1567
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1141, wR ₂ = 0.1864
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.55/-0.34

[a] Weighting scheme:: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0751P)^2 + 0.1923P]$ where $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Secondary extinction expression (SHELXL-type): $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table S10. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1b**.

Identification code	b20230136_EM663DUCu4
Empirical formula	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ BF ₂ N ₂ O ₃
Formula weight	414.25
Temperature/K	170.01(10)
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
a/Å	21.2016(3)
b/Å	7.13862(9)
c/Å	27.9608(4)
α /°	90.0
β /°	108.2938(17)
γ /°	90.0
Volume/Å ³	4018.00(10)
Z	8
ρ_{calc} /cm ³	1.370
μ /mm ⁻¹	0.854
F(000)	1744.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.237 × 0.181 × 0.065
Radiation	CuK α (λ = 1.54184)
2 θ range for data collection/°	6.66 to 147.124
Index ranges	-26 ≤ h ≤ 18, -8 ≤ k ≤ 8, -33 ≤ l ≤ 34
Reflections collected	20057
Independent reflections	4015 [R _{int} = 0.0333, R _{sigma} = 0.0257]
Data/restraints/parameters	4015/0/278
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.081
Final R indexes [I >= 2 σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0354, wR ₂ = 0.0930
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0394, wR ₂ = 0.0959
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.22/-0.20

[a] Weighting scheme:: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0751P)^2 + 0.1923P]$ where $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Secondary extinction expression (SHELXL-type): $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table S11. Crystal data and structure refinement for **2b**.

Identification code	b20240205_EM665DUMo
Empirical formula	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ BN ₄ O ₃
Formula weight	428.29
Temperature/K	170.00(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	9.0878(3)
b/Å	10.9478(4)
c/Å	11.6685(4)
α/°	106.973(3)
β/°	91.387(3)
γ/°	92.478(3)
Volume/Å ³	1108.48(7)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.283
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.086
F(000)	452.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.321 × 0.172 × 0.109
Radiation	Mo Kα (λ = 0.71073)
2θ range for data collection/°	4.49 to 53.998
Index ranges	-11 ≤ h ≤ 11, -13 ≤ k ≤ 13, -14 ≤ l ≤ 14
Reflections collected	13442
Independent reflections	4802 [R _{int} = 0.0418, R _{sigma} = 0.0424]
Data/restraints/parameters	4802/0/296
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.047
Final R indexes [I >= 2σ(I)]	R ₁ = 0.0568, wR ₂ = 0.1673
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0694, wR ₂ = 0.1804
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.48/-0.36

[a] Weighting scheme: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0751P)^2 + 0.1923P]$ where $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Secondary extinction expression (SHELXL-type): $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table S12. Crystal data and structure refinement for **3b**.

Identification code	b20230133_NMB15DUCuB
Empirical formula	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ BN ₂ O ₇
Formula weight	464.27
Temperature/K	170.00(10)
Crystal system	orthorhombic
Space group	Pbcn
a/Å	22.7228(7)
b/Å	7.0845(3)
c/Å	27.2192(16)
α /°	90.0
β /°	90.0
γ /°	90.0
Volume/Å ³	4381.7(4)
Z	8
ρ_{calc} /cm ³	1.408
μ /mm ⁻¹	0.854
F(000)	1952.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.529 × 0.096 × 0.03
Radiation	Cu K α (λ = 1.54184)
2 θ range for data collection/°	6.494 to 137.926
Index ranges	-27 ≤ h ≤ 27, -8 ≤ k ≤ 7, -32 ≤ l ≤ 32
Reflections collected	38678
Independent reflections	4080 [R _{int} = 0.1833, R _{sigma} = 0.0903]
Data/restraints/parameters	4080/0/314
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.157
Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$]	R ₁ = 0.1052, wR ₂ = 0.2574
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1445, wR ₂ = 0.2900
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.28/-0.43

[a] Weighting scheme:: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0751P)^2 + 0.1923P]$ where $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Secondary extinction expression (SHELXL-type): $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

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